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Research Article

**ALCOHOL: A FORENSIC AND PHARMACOLOGICAL
PERSPECTIVE****Ashique Ali Arain¹, Shahla Imran², Madiha Shah³, Haya Memon⁴, Shahzad Ahmedani⁵,
Shehnaz Bano Memon⁶**¹MBBS, MCPS (Family Medicine), M. Phil (Pharmacology), Assistant Professor,
Department of Pharmacology, Muhammad Medical College Mirpurkhas, Sindh, Pakistan² MBBS, DMJ, Assistant Professor, Department of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology,
Bilawal Medical College, LUMHS, Jamshoro, Sindh, Pakistan³MBBS, FCPS (Medicine), Assistant Professor, Department of Medicine, Liaquat University
of Medical and Health Sciences, Sindh, Pakistan⁴MBBS, Lecturer, Department of Forensic Medicine, Indus Medical College, Tando
Muhammad Khan, Sindh, Pakistan⁵MBBS, Lecturer, Department of Forensic Medicine, Bilawal Medical College, LUMHS,
Jamshoro⁶MBBS, M. Phil (Pharmacology), Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Isra
University Hyderabad**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Alcohol consuming habit is observed in almost all countries of the world despite of the legal and religious limitations in various regions of the land. Islam bans the use of alcohol claiming fewer advantages and more disadvantages associated with its use and loss of cognitive functions. Pakistan is an Islamic republic with strict law about alcoholism. The current work was based on 107 participants using convenient sampling for with confidentiality of the individuals for obtaining information related to alcohol consumption in district Hyderabad 100% of cases were male with age ranging from 30 to 45 Years. Most of the participants (50%) were of opinion that alcohol is consumed as a habit just for enjoyment while 38% thinks it as a source of suppression of worries and various social natures of stress and 12 % people thought a mixture of the two conditions as a remedy for stress and worries of daily life along with habit.

Conclusion: We found alcohol as a sin more than a remedy as a conclusion of this work.

Key Words: Alcohol, Prohibited, stress, disadvantages.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Ashique Ali Arain,**

MBBS, MCPS (Family Medicine), M. Phil (Pharmacology)

Assistant Professor

Department of Pharmacology

Muhammad Medical College Mirpurkhas

Email.ashiquepcmd77@yahoo.com, Cell No. 03333389250

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Alcohol absorption occurs via stomach as well as duodenum, reaching its peak plasma levels within 1 hour following ingestion. It is metabolized by alcohol dehydrogenase first into acetaldehyde which gets converted into acetate by the enzyme aldehyde dehydrogenase in the liver. Alcohol follows zero-order elimination with 15-40 mg/dL/h. Thiamine and folic acid are used for the prevention as well as the treatment of alcohol associated Wernicke encephalopathy and macrocytic anemia respectively [1]. Alcoholism is an underlying etiology for >30 diseases conditions including various infections, different cancers, diabetes mellitus, alcohol use disorder, pancreatitis, hepatic and cardiac diseases along with multiple medicolegal issues [2]. Alcohol is the oldest substance probably used by human being as the history refers this matter will before the 1400 years in the period before the Islamic revelation. The probable reason for use was its few potentials benefits but the harms were more than the expected benefits so Islam completely prohibited the use in a gradual way. The 10th edition ICD-10 (International Classification of Diseases) has provided detailed information for various such condition along with their codes likewise E24.4 for Alcohol induced pseudo Cushing's syndrome, F10 for mental and behavioral disorders attributed to use of alcohol, F10.0 was given to Acute alcohol intoxication, F10.1 for the Harmful use of alcohol, F10.2 represents the alcohol dependence syndrome, F10.3 shows alcohol withdrawal state, F10.4 shows delirium due to alcohol withdrawal F10.5 was used for Psychotic disorders associated with alcohol, F10.6 for Amnesic syndrome, F10.7 is given to late and residual psychotic disorders, F10.8 Other mental and behavioral disorders, F10.9 for mental as well as behavioral condition of unspecified nature, G31.2 to alcohol attributed neuro degeneration, G62.1 was the code for alcoholic polyneuropathy, G72.1 represented the myopathy related to alcohol I42.6 represented alcoholic induced cardiomyopathy, K29.2 for alcoholic related gastritis, K70 alcoholic liver diseases,

K70.0 for fatty liver due to alcohol, K70.1 for alcohol induced hepatitis, K70.2 was used for hepatic fibrosis and sclerosis due to alcohol, K70.3 for liver cirrhosis of alcohol use and K70.4 was the code hepatic failure due to alcoholism, K70.9 was the unspecified hepatic condition associated with alcohol, K85.2 coded acute pancreatitis of alcohol origin the same condition in chronic form was coded K86.0, similarly there were many other alcohol related conditions including maternal and fetal abnormalities [2]]. The alcohol related mortality was estimated as 2.5 million deaths per year and 9% of which are in below 30 year age group [3]. Alcoholism was reported to be the 7th risk factor for 2-2% deaths in female and 6-8% in male <50 years old people [4]. The most common substance to be encountered in the forensic toxicology is the alcohol and its quantity of intake is important for deciding the criminal as well as civil cases in forensic medicine [5].

METHODOLOGY:

This study was of cross sectional design survey based on questionnaire specifically designed for evaluating the attitude of alcoholic by volunteer participants. The inclusion was male gender and age ranging between 30 years to 45 years without religious discrimination. Females and adolescents were excluded from study along with the medicolegal cases. The response was obtained in percentage from 106 participants from Hyderabad Sindh, Pakistan. Data acquired with the frequency and percentage was presented in tables represented by bar charts.

RESULTS:

Alcohol consumption trend as an enjoyment was reported by 50% of the study participants while the consumption of alcohol as self-considered remedy was the opinion of 39% of the study participants. Both the above mentioned reasons were believed by some 11% of the study subjects out of the 106 surveyed individuals. The mean age of study participants was 40± 3 years.

Table 1: The frequency and percentage of probable reasons for alcohol intake

S. No	Parameters	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Alcohol as enjoyment	53	50%
2.	Alcohol as remedy	41	39%
3.	Both	12	11%
4.	Total	106	100%

Fig-1: Frequency distribution for reasons of alcohol intake

DISCUSSION:

Alcohol drinking is a habit found globally as well as Pakistan and other Islamic countries despite of the strict prohibition. The use and sale of alcohol is not allowed by law in Pakistan but unfortunately this is abused increasingly due to many reasons [6]. Effects of alcohol are mediated through variety of neurotransmitters like dopamine, GABA as it does not have specific receptors so pharmacological agents are focused to interfere with these neurotransmitters. Currently available drugs to treat alcoholism are Naltrexone, (a μ -opioid antagonist) which blocks the ventral tegmental opioid receptors so inhibits the dopamine release, Acamprosate (a taurine analog) used as an anti-relapse drug to treat alcohol dependence, disulfiram (an inhibitor of the alcohol-dehydrogenase) which prevents the metabolism of acetaldehyde which gets accumulated in the body resulting into flushing, headache and chest pain on alcohol intake which prevents the patient from alcoholism and Nalmefene, an antagonist opioid at opioid receptors a relatively new drug for alcohol dependence [7,8]. The autopsy with multiple alcohol-related pathologies creates problems for forensic pathologist in assigning a single underlying cause of death [9]. The abuse of alcohol may lead to the negative results that often results into criminal charges. If an individual is suspected of driving under the influence, law enforcement agents can determine the extent of intoxication by measuring the blood alcohol concentration and performing actions taking place after alcohol intoxication depends on whether the intoxication was involuntary or voluntary [10]. This study was aimed for assessing the opinion of individuals

regarding the alcohol usage by various people of our society and found all of them disliking the alcoholism even the non-Muslims but unfortunately there needs much more efforts on government level to make public awareness about the adverse effects of alcohol on various body organs and system. What is currently being practiced is limited to the forensic department specially the medicolegal cases. Campaigns similar to anti-smoking and other programs of public interest need to be arranged at public levels so that masses at larger scales are motivated as we are much behind from the developed nations.

CONCLUSION:

Alcohol is a sin by either way if someone takes it as an enjoyment or a self-considered drug.

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